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THE EFFECT OF THE WAR ON THE DIGITALIZATION OF THE INSURANCE SERVICES MARKET OF UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The war brought many challenges, including an increase in insurance claims, the need for prompt payment, compensation and maintaining customer confidence. The development of the Ukrainian insurance market is accompanied by other problems, in particular, imperfect supervision of the financial services market, the national economy is in a state of crisis, a lack of innovation, and a certain distrust of consumers in insurance services. At the same time, the war stimulated the acceleration of digitization, which can become the foundation for the further development of the insurance market in Ukraine. Digitization of the insurance market during wartime is a necessity that helps maintain the stability and reliability of insurance services, even in the most difficult times.

Keywords: digitization, mortgage market, insurance services, war.

Formulation of the problem. Today, the market of insurance services in Ukraine is in a difficult situation, which is caused both by global trends and problems associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, and by the situation caused by a full-scale invasion. Despite the difficult conditions in which all branches of the economy are, this is a time that allows improving processes, looking for optimal models of interaction and steps for market development.

The events of the last year have demonstrated the importance of digitalization in all aspects of life, which has led not only to talk about digital transformation, but also to its widespread implementation in order to preserve business.

In all developed countries, insurance is a strategically important branch of the economy, providing the majority of investments in its development and freeing state budgets from the costs of indemnifying losses from unforeseen events.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Questions related to the development of the insurance market and the involvement of modern technologies were and continue to be dealt with by a large number of scientists and scientists, in particular: V. Bazilevich, S. Volosovych, Yu. Zavaloka, M. Demyanchuk, R. Zheliznyak, N. Kraus, M. Müller, V. Nechiporenko, R. Pikus, and others.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. The development of insurance in Ukraine is one of the key areas of modern activity. These decisions are aimed at overcoming negative trends, which include problems related to the demographic situation, COVID-19 and military actions, which have affected the emergence of a number of problematic issues that require immediate solutions.

The purpose of the work. Based on the above issues, it is advisable to investigate the importance of the digitalization of the insurance market in Ukraine under the influence of COVID-19 and active military operations, which will allow to satisfy the complex and individual needs of customers and will become a driving force that will contribute to the transformation of insurance companies and the creation of digital personalized service platforms.

Results. With the expansion of digital technologies in the insurance industry, the main driving force of the digital transformation of insurance is to meet the more complex demands of consumers. Currently, the insurance industry of Ukraine is in the process of digitization. With the help of information technologies such as artificial intelligence technology, blockchain technology, cloud computing technology, big data processing technology and Internet of Things technology, the digitalization of insurance has become an inevitable trend in the development of the national insurance industry. The insurance industry is one of the fastest growing sectors of the national economy in the digital era [3, p. 272].

The inevitable result of any war is destruction and devastation. Insurance is a mechanism for providing compensation for losses. Different insurance companies have different war clauses in their insurance contracts, so it is important to research the specific terms of the contract.

Admittedly, the key factor here is whether there is an actual causal relationship between the military activities. The introduction of military actions and specific damage, namely the state of war, should not be a reason for not admitting a case to insurance and refusing to pay insurance compensation.

The development of the Ukrainian insurance market was accompanied by other problems, in particular, a sharp drop in demand for insurance. In the country, there is imperfect supervision of the financial services market, the national economy is in a state of crisis, there is a lack of innovation, and there is a certain mistrust of consumers in insurance services. As a result, the Ukrainian insurance market cannot function normally as part of the country's economic system. In a word, it is necessary to look for ways of further development of the domestic insurance market, which will contribute to the elimination of the negative consequences of economic risks and contribute to the overall development of the national economy.

The corona crisis intensified existing problems in the insurance industry, forced insurers to build a new business model adequate to the requirements of the situation in the economy of countries and on financial markets. It can already be pointed out that the established business models in the insurance sector will not change significantly and will not return to their previous state.

Improving the functioning of the insurance market of Ukraine may include various directions and measures to improve the regulation, safety, accessibility and competitiveness of this industry. The main areas of improvement of the insurance market of Ukraine are:

- adaptation of legislation to international standards and insurance practices to attract foreign investors and increase trust in insurance companies of Ukraine;
- introduction of modern information technologies, such as artificial intelligence, blockchain and others, to improve customer service, optimize processes and reduce risks;
- expansion of online sales of insurance products and services to facilitate access to insurance protection for customers;
- improvement of mechanisms for detecting and preventing insurance fraud, which contributes to reducing insurance losses and increasing consumer confidence;
- the development of cyber insurance and protection against cyber threats, as this industry is becoming increasingly important in the era of digital transformation;
- promotion of increased competition in the insurance market to improve the quality and availability of insurance services;
- development of innovative insurance products and services that meet the needs of the modern consumer.

These directions can contribute to improving the efficiency and development of the insurance market of Ukraine, providing high-quality insurance protection for clients and contributing to the stability and competitiveness of this industry.

In the modern insurance market, the main directions of digitalization are several important trends: Internetization, individualization and digitalization of insurance activities.

Internetization - involves the active use of the Internet for all aspects of insurance activities, including

the sale of insurance policies, customer service and risk management. Online platforms allow customers to conveniently choose and buy insurance products online. The process of internetization in insurance activity is carried out by insurance companies not only by selling insurance services via the Internet, but also by collecting information about policyholders via the network and settling insurance cases via the Internet.

Personalization - modern technologies allow insurance companies to create individual insurance solutions for each client based on their insurance profile and needs. Data analytics and algorithms determine insurance risk and offer personalized solutions. The individualization of economic relations in the insurance market includes the creation of individual insurance offers for customers, the departure from mass standardized products and the use of large databases, new production technologies and wireless communication to collect an expanded set of data on policyholders and insurance objects. Individualization also involves an individual risk assessment based on increasing the amount of information collected about the insured and the object of insurance, and the formation of individual insurance offers based on the client's request.

Digitization means the complete digital transformation of an insurance company's internal processes, including automation of contract signing, claims processing and internal communication. Digitalization improves the efficiency and speed of customer service.

These trends highlight the importance of insurance companies adapting to the digital environment to provide greater accessibility, efficiency and convenience for customers.

Thanks to digital technology, the online insurance business has diversified, offering a variety of insurance products and accumulating huge customer resources, which has significantly increased their satisfaction. At the same time, income from insurance premiums on the Internet also increased, and the operating profit of large insurance companies increased significantly.

The digital transformation of insurance requires professional talent. The digital transformation of insurance requires the use of a large amount of statistical data and information technologies, so the insurance industry must pay attention to the problem of insufficient personnel reserves in the new situation. As digital transformation deepens, insurance companies will face a lack of digitization.

This is due to the complex use of biotechnology, image recognition, artificial intelligence, big data and other technologies during the digitization of insurance.

Thus, insurance companies must consciously build a digital platform team. On the one hand, they should actively expand the circle of recruiters. They should no longer use a narrow vision and only recruit talent at the insurance level. They should be active for those involved in programming, applying talents with experience in the field of science and technology.

On the other hand, it is necessary to actively conduct digital transformation training for existing personnel and make timely adjustments to their career planning and job certification. As the digitalization of insurance develops on a global scale, insurance companies

must also consider creating a corporate culture with a digital model in the process of completing the digital transformation.

Digital insurance replaces traditional insurance. The digitalization of insurance may encourage the insurance industry to optimize its business and increase efficiency, but it still takes time to merge with traditional insurance. Traditional sales methods that rely on insurance agents or intermediaries will be affected by buying methods through digital channels. With the help of the Internet, clients have opened the channels of insurance companies. Virtually all procedures are streamlined from purchase, extension to claim filing and these processes can be streamlined through digital procedures, showing that the digitization of insurance allows customers to avoid cumbersome claims. During this process, insurance companies need to intelligently solve problems related to changes in the content of the work of industry practitioners caused by changes in traditional insurance.

A study conducted by the Z / Yen company with the support of PwC shows that the insurance market positively perceives the implementation of block-chain solutions [8].

The potential of blockchain technology in the field of financial services is enormous. Recent estimates from experts at PwC confirm this. The implementation of blockchain systems in the banking sector, in particular in the process of pre-screening customers and combating money laundering, could lead to savings in the amount of 2.5 billion dollars. These savings represent a fraction of the total \$10 billion spent annually on information processing in this sector. [1, p. 15].

However, the insurance sector's interest in block chain is not limited to these potential benefits. Blockchain technology has the potential to be key to changing approaches in the insurance industry. It helps to reduce costs and increase the efficiency of processes, and can also radically change the methods of work in this industry, which will contribute to the growth of profits and the development of the sector. Insurance consumers will be served by blockchain-based transactions, eliminating the need for intermediaries and ensuring accurate records of documents. It will also allow the creation of a single global and reliable database, which did not exist before.

Companies such as Z/Yen and PwC note that blockchain can improve relationships between insurers, consumers, regulators and business partners. This technology can help speed up the decision-making process and increase the accuracy of data sharing in these relationships. [8].

The use of blockchain technology can really optimize the process of registration of insurance portfolios and improve the management of insurance payments. A portfolio created with the help of blockchain will be able to automatically adjust insurance payments in real time, while increasing the level of anonymity and protection of health data. Blockchain technology can also be used to protect medical records from unauthorized changes or falsification. Medical documents will be signed using the SHA-256 algorithm, which converts

the signature into a Bitcoin address. After that, the originality of the document can be verified in the Bitcoin blockchain. Such measures will help prevent data manipulation and increase trust in scientific research and insurance companies. [7, p. 512].

Process automation, content creation and evaluation, and advanced imaging technologies will drive business growth, especially in the areas of data analysis and customer support. This allows to achieve new strategic flexibility, which gives important competitive advantages. However, to do so, they must ensure that lack of AI expertise, both technical and business, is not a limiting factor. Therefore, partnerships, funding and investments in cloud AI solutions should also be considered.

AI tools and automation strategies are revolutionizing the development process with AI-assisted design. This will lead to improved software quality, improved testing efficiency, and faster release cycles. AI simplifies code inspection and error detection, supports the development of low-code and no-code platforms, and automates documentation to ensure reliable software quality. The main goal is to use scarce engineering resources as efficiently as possible by automating routine tasks with AI.

Most insurers already using AI technology have focused their investments on customer service projects such as chatbots. This allows them to automatically retrieve customer information and respond to inquiries. The research found that the top insurance chatbot applications include product management, marketing, policy underwriting and acquisition, policy servicing and claims management. In addition, the study also showed that insurance company executives who were familiar with existing AI projects in their companies most often cited projects related to customer service (56%). This is likely because chatbots allow customers to receive personalized product and pricing recommendations almost instantly, giving consumers and business customers the ability to purchase most insurance products online in minutes.

AI technologies can now also be applied to more data sources to improve the accuracy of risk assessments and quotes. For example, these tools can automatically analyze real-time data from security systems or drones when underwriting homeowner insurance applications.

The claims process is another area where AI can be applied to automatically audit thousands of open claims while actionable, rather than reviewing a sample of claims after they've closed. In this way, insurers will be able to move beyond the traditional reactive model of paying claims after a loss and will be able to adopt a proactive, preventive model to help customers avoid losses.

The security and efficiency of online interactions are paramount, especially in the insurance industry, where customer relationships are built on trust. To promote digital trust in insurance, much can be done to establish transparency and effective customer interaction at every relevant touchpoint.

Much can be done to increase digital trust in insurance by ensuring transparency and effective customer

engagement at every relevant touchpoint. ISACA defines digital trust as "confidence in the integrity of relationships, interactions, and transactions between suppliers and consumers within a connected digital ecosystem." PwC sees digital trust exclusively as cyber security from a business perspective. All studies come to the same conclusion: the right digital trust is beneficial for the insurance business. The first is reliability (availability, functionality, convenience); second, security (data privacy, data ethics, secure transactions and asset preservation); and third, reassurance (integrity of decision-making and interaction with an emotionally literate technician).

Immersive virtual reality technologies such as AR and VR are changing the customer experience: increasing engagement and brand awareness, and creating innovative business strategies. These technologies increase customer loyalty and create memorable stories that increase brand awareness. They also support decision-making with real-time data visualization, which simplifies complex processes with simulated environments and secure test scenarios. Virtual training optimizes employee performance, and augmented reality-supported service and operational processes increase efficiency and minimize errors.

Sustainable technologies support responsible corporate governance and thus provide long-term competitive advantages. With ESG (Environmental, social, and governance)-compliant technology and data strategy, which is a key means of climate neutrality, ESG will become an integral part of corporate transformation after digitalization – not in terms of regulation, but increasingly in the sense of increasing company value.

Also an important aspect of digitalization is the creation of online stores of insurance companies, where customers can purchase various types of insurance online, including property insurance, travel insurance, CASCO, health and accident insurance. The possibility of online payment is also being actively implemented by insurance companies in cooperation with banks. [2, p. 17].

Some insurance organizations have already realized the possibility of creating online offices for their clients. In such offices, clients can view the list of current insurance contracts, track the payment of the insurance premium and find information about the next payments. However, so far this option is available only in a limited number of insurance companies, and their share is only 9%.

This digital initiative aims to make it easier for customers to interact with insurance companies and improve access to information about their insurance policies. Although these are the only percentages so far, this indicates that the insurance industry is gradually moving towards digital transformation and facilitating customer service through online platforms [6, p. 277].

The implementation of cloud technologies is becoming relevant for insurance companies in Ukraine. For example, UNIKA Insurance Company PJSC implements its activities in the De Novo cloud environment.

This initiative shows that insurance companies understand the importance of using modern technologies to optimize their activities and improve customer service.

Cloud technologies allow you to store and process data in a safe and accessible way, and also simplify work with a large amount of information. This can lead to an increase in the efficiency of insurance companies and improve their customer service.

When researching insurance companies' websites, it's important to note that many of them provide links to their mobile apps. Today, insurance companies such as UNIKA Insurance Company PJSC, Ingo Ukraine PJSC, Ukrainian Joint Stock Insurance Company Aska PJSC, Insurance Company LLC and many others have such applications.

These insurance company apps help customers calculate the cost of an insurance policy, make an online premium payment, make an appointment with a doctor and upload personal documents for insurance benefits. They make the process of obtaining insurance services more convenient and accessible for customers.

Another important digital initiative being implemented in the Ukrainian insurance market is telematics. Telematics in insurance includes the process of specifying the cost of an insurance policy for each individual policyholder with the help of technical devices. This monitoring system monitors the policyholder's behavior and helps to establish more individual tariffs. [4, p. 33].

Telematics devices that transmit information to cloud storage for further analysis and display in a mobile application are a modern and advanced technology. It is not even necessary to install a physical telematics device, as you can use a special application on your smartphone for this purpose. In the insurance market in Ukraine, such services are provided by insurance companies, such as PJSC "Insurance Company "ARKS" Insurance", PJSC "Ukrainian Joint-Stock Insurance Company "ASKA", PJSC "Joint-Stock Insurance Company "INGO Ukraine".

Conclusions. Despite the expected only positive effect, the implementation of digitalization processes in insurance may be accompanied by possible negative consequences, namely, the low level of implementation of domestic developments of insurance digitalization software; lagging behind leading foreign countries in the creation, development and mastering of competitive information technologies used in insurance; insufficient level of information security; emergence of mistrust in the digital environment in general and in insurance in particular.

In addition, in modern realities, one cannot fail to note the risks that both the entire insurance industry and its individual participants may face in connection with the impact of the war on the entire economy of Ukraine.

In order to increase the effectiveness of the impact of digitalization on the insurance sphere, one of the most important tasks is to determine these possible negative consequences, as well as the development of management decisions to prevent them or reduce the amount of damage caused by their implementation.

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